

FATIGUE CRACK PROPAGATION MECHANISMS OF CORE-SHELL RUBBER MODIFIED EPOXY RESINS

Satoshi Matsuda*¹, Yoshio Furukawa², Hajime Kishi¹

¹Department of Chemical Engineering and Materials Science, University of Hyogo,
2167 Shosha, Himeji, 671-2280 Japan
Email: smatsuda@eng.u-hyogo.ac.jp

² Kaneka Corporation,
Takasago, Japan

Keywords: Epoxy resin, Core-shell Rubber, Fatigue Crack Propagation

ABSTRACT

Epoxy resins are utilized in various industrial areas as adhesives and matrix of composite materials because of the higher stiffness, strength and heat resistance. Toughening with rubber particles is one of the most popular method to enhance the fracture toughness. For the structure uses, the fatigue resistance is very important property as well as the static mechanical properties. In this study the effect of molecular weight between crosslinks (crosslink density) on the fatigue crack propagation properties of rubber-toughened epoxy resin. Several DGEBA epoxy resins with different average molecular weight were used in this study. Core shell rubber (CSR) particles, the diameter of 100nm, were well dispersed in the epoxy. The fracture toughness of Core Shell Rubber-modified epoxy monotonously enhanced with increasing molecular weight between crosslinks, and the effect of core-shell rubber became larger as the molecular weight between crosslink increased. On the other hand, the fatigue threshold had a peak against molecular weight between crosslinks. Whereas there is positive effect of core shell rubber in fatigue resistance for molecular weight between crosslink of 1440g/mol, the fatigue threshold of the core shell rubber modified epoxy is lower than that of unmodified one for molecular weight between crosslinks of 3040g/mol. TEM observation from the side surface of the crack tip revealed that the size of the plastic deformation zone was well related to the fatigue resistance. The core shell rubber particles enhanced the shear plastic deformation region at the crack tip for molecular weight between crosslinks of 1440g/mol, and the particles largely lowered the deformation region. These results was caused by the deformation ability of the epoxy resin under plane-stress state.

1 INTRODUCTION

Epoxy resins are utilized as the structural adhesive, matrix resin of composite materials because of their high stiffness and strength. The epoxy resins are so brittle that the toughening was used to enhance the fracture toughness. Insertion of the rubber particles or alloy with engineering thermoplastic like polyethersulfone (PES) or polyetherimide is very common way for the toughening of the epoxy resin [1-4]. Carboxyl - terminated butadiene - nitrile rubber (CTBN) is effective way to improve the fracture toughness[5-8]. In these cases it is not easy to control the phase structure because reaction induced phase separation depends on the curing condition. Toughening by addition of the rubber particles like core shell rubber is very simple method in comparison with phase-separation technique [9-11].

When structures are designed, application of cyclic load is considered for the long time reliability. The fatigue resistance of the material is very important property as well as the static mechanical properties. In particular the evaluation of the fatigue threshold value is essential to the structural design. However the fracture mechanism of the epoxy resin near the fatigue threshold is not clear. To clarify the fatigue mechanism the mechanical properties must be discussed on the basis of the microstructure of the epoxy resin. In this study the effect of molecular weight between crosslinks (crosslink density) on the fatigue crack propagation properties of rubber-toughened epoxy resin.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Materials

Epoxy resins used in this study were six types of Bisphenol A diglycidyl ether (DGEBA) with different average molecular weight. Hardener was diaminodiphenylsulfone (DDS). The chemical structure of DGEBA epoxy and DDS were shown in Figure 1 and 2, respectively. Core-shell rubber (CSR) particles supplied by Kaneka Corporation were used as toughening modifier. The particle diameter was 100nm. They are consisted of polymethylmethacrylate (PMMA) shell and poly-n-butyl Acrylate (P-n-BA) core. CSR particles and DDS were added into the pre-heated epoxy resin and well stirred. After degassed, the mixture was poured into the mold and heated in the oven at 130oC for 3hours as pre-cure and 150oC for 3hours as post-cure. The specimens were cut from the plates.

Figure 1 Chemical structure of DGEBA.

Figure 2 Chemical structure of DDS.

Figure 3 shows dynamic viscoelastic behaviours of the cured resins. The glass transition temperature (temperature of $\tan \delta$ peak) was higher as the average molecular weight of the epoxy oligomer became lower. The molecular weight between crosslinks, M_c , was calculated from eq.(1).

$$M_c = \frac{3\phi\rho RT_R}{E_R} \quad (1),$$

here ϕ is front factor (1.3), ρ is density of cured resin, R is gas constant (8.31J/mol K), E_R is storage modulus of rubbery plateau and T_R is minimum temperature at rubbery state. M_c is often utilized to show reciprocal factor of crosslink density.

Figure 3 Dynamic viscoelastic behaviours of the cured resin.

2.2 Fracture toughness and Fatigue crack propagation tests

Fracture toughness tests were carried out using compact tension specimens in accordance with ASTM D5045. Specimen configuration was shown in Fig.4. The width, W , and the thickness, B , was 32.5mm and 6mm, respectively. The specimens were loaded by a mechanical testing machine (Shimadzu, AG-10kN) at constant displacement rate of 5mm/min. Fracture toughness was calculated from eq.(2) using maximum load, P_{\max} , and crack length, a .

$$K_{Ic} = \frac{P_{\max}}{BW^{1/2}} f\left(\frac{a}{W}\right) \quad (2)$$

$$f\left(\frac{a}{W}\right) = \frac{(2 + a/W)(0.886 + 4.64a/W - 13.32a^2/W^2 + 14.72a^3/W^3 - 5.6a^4/W^4)}{(1 - a/W)^{3/2}}$$

Fatigue crack propagation tests were carried out using compact tension specimens with servo hydraulic fatigue testing machine (Shimadzu servopulser EHF-FD1). The loading profile was sinusoidal wave of 1Hz, and stress ratio was 0.1. Stress intensity range, ΔK , was controlled automatically to decrease as increasing the crack length during the testing.

Figure 4 Schematics of compact tension specimen ($B=32.5\text{mm}$, $W=6\text{mm}$).

2.2 Fractographic observation

After the fatigue crack propagation tests, the fracture surfaces were observed by a scanning electron microscope (JEOL, JSM-7001). The crack tips after the fatigue fracture were also observed from the side surface by a transmission electron microscope. The sections were cut from the specimens around the crack tip using a microtome and were stained with Ruthenium tetroxide (RuO_4).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Fracture toughness and Fatigue Crack propagation behavior

Fig.5 shows results of the fracture toughness tests. Open and closed symbols show the results of the neat resin without core-shell rubber (CSR) and those of the resin with 5wt% CSR. The fracture toughness of the neat resin increased slightly with increasing molecular weight between crosslinks, M_c . On the other hand, the toughness values of CSR-modified epoxy was much improved as M_c increased. The results shows that the effect of CSR particles on the fracture surface of the epoxy resin largely depends on the matrix resin property and was larger as crosslink density decreased.

Fig.6 shows relation between fatigue threshold, ΔK_{th} , and molecular weight between crosslinks. The tendency of ΔK_{th} of the neat resin is similar to that of the fracture toughness of the neat resin. However, the fatigue threshold of CSR-modified epoxy was different from that of the fracture toughness of the CSR-modified epoxy which was monotonously increased. The fatigue threshold increased at lower M_c , got a peak at 1100g/mol of M_c and decreased in higher M_c region.

For 3060g/mol of M_c , the CSR reduced the fatigue threshold of the neat resin and had the negative effect. This means that the fracture mechanism under fatigue threshold was totally different from that of the static fracture.

Figure 5 Relation between fracture toughness and molecular weight between crosslinks.

Figure 6 Relation between fatigue threshold and molecular weight between crosslinks.

3.2 Microscopic observation

Fig.7 shows fatigue fracture surfaces near the threshold region of the CSR-modified epoxy resins. Photos on the left side and the right side indicate the surfaces of the neat resin and CSR modified resin, respectively. The surfaces of the neat resin was almost flat regardless of the molecular weight between crosslinks. For the CSR-modified epoxy of the 520 and 1440g/mol of M_c , there were many small holes on the surfaces, showing that the rubber particles cavitated during the fatigue fracture process. The size of the holes in 1440g/mol of M_c was bigger than the original particle size (100nm). This means the occurrence of the plastic deformation of the epoxy resin around the rubber particles and the increase in dissipated energy during crack propagation. For the CSR-modified epoxy of the higher M_c , the net-like structure can be observed on the whole surface. The “net” around the holes were drawing largely. The cavitation of the rubber particles facilitates the surrounding matrix resin at the crack tip owing to the shift from tri-axial tensile stress state to mono axial tensile stress. This structure was formed by the highly strained epoxy resin around the holes and the enlargement of the cavitated holes only in the case of the epoxy resin with low crosslink density (high M_c) which has

large breaking strain. Normally highly strained deformation of resin leads to large enhancement of fracture energy and higher fatigue threshold for crack propagation. However the fatigue threshold of the CSR-modified epoxy resin of 3060g/mol which showed the net-like structure was much lower than that of unmodified one. The results of the fatigue tests could not be explained by the fractographic observation.

Fig.8 shows transmission electron micrographs of the side surfaces at the crack tip of the CSR-modified epoxy resins. White region from left side of the photo is main crack and white and grey holes indicate the cavitated and the uncavitated CSR, respectively. For the epoxy with 520g/mol of Mc the rubber particles were cavitated but the shapes were almost round, showing that the deformation of the epoxy matrix is small. For the epoxy with 1440g/mol of Mc the crack tip was blunt and the cavitated holes around the crack tip was elongated to the elliptical shape. The deformation region was expanded to 2 or 3 μm from the crack tip. On the other hand, for the epoxy with higher Mc the main crack was jagged. Most of the rubber particles remained and the cavitated voids were expanded ahead. The crack propagation was caused by the connection of the grown voids. Whereas only epoxy on the fracture surface was highly elongated, the surrounding epoxy did not deform. As the energy dissipation occurred in the local region just on the crack line, total quantity of the dissipated energy was small. For the unmodified epoxy with 3060g/mol of Mc, the plastic deformation is expected to expand around the crack tip and the energy would be gained from the whole plastic deformation zone. That is the reason why the core-shell rubber reduce the fatigue threshold for the higher molecular weight between crosslinks.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The effect of molecular weight between crosslinks on the fatigue crack propagation properties of rubber-toughened epoxy resin. The fracture toughness of Core Shell Rubber-modified epoxy monotonously enhanced with increasing molecular weight between crosslinks, and the effect of core-shell rubber became larger as the molecular weight between crosslink increased. On the other hand, the fatigue threshold had a peak against molecular weight between crosslinks. Whereas there is positive effect of core shell rubber in fatigue resistance for molecular weight between crosslink of 1440g/mol, the fatigue threshold of the core shell rubber modified epoxy is lower than that of unmodified one for molecular weight between crosslinks of 3060g/mol. TEM observation from the side surface of the crack tip revealed that the size of the plastic deformation zone was well related to the fatigue resistance. The core shell rubber particles enhanced the shear plastic deformation region at the crack tip for molecular weight between crosslinks of 1440g/mol, and the particles largely lowered the deformation region. These results was caused by the deformation ability of the epoxy resin under plane-stress state.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. A. Pearson, A. F. Yee, *Polymer*, 34, 17, 3658-3670 (1993)
- [2] C. B. Bucknall, C. M. Gomez, I. Quintard, *Polymer*, 35, 2, 353-359(1994)
- [3] H. Kishi, Y-B.Shi, J.Huang and A.F.Yee, *J.Mater.Sci*, 33, 3479-3488 (1998)
- [4] A. J. Kinloch, M. L. Yuen, S. D. Jenkins, *Journal of Materials Science*, 29, 14, 3781-3790 (1994)
- [5] A.F.Yee and R.A.Pearson, *J Mater Sci*, 21, 2462-2474 (1986)
- [6] H.R.azimi, R.A. Pearson, R.W. Hertzberg, *J. Mater. Sci*,31,3777-3789(1996)
- [7] S.C. Kunz, J.A. Sayre, R.A. Assink, *Polymer*, 23, 13, 1897-1906(1982)
- [8] A.J.Kinloch, S.J.Shaw, D.A.Tod and D.L.Hunston, *Polymer*, 24, 1341-1354 (1983)
- [9] H-J. Sue, *Journal of Materials Science*, 27, 11, 3098-3107(1992)
- [10] F. Lu, W. J Cantwell, H. H Kausch, *Journal of Materials Science*, 32, 11, 3055-3059(1997)
- [11] L. Becu, A. Maazouz, H. Sautereau, J.F.Gerard, *J Applied Polym Sci*, 65, 2419-2431 (1997)

Figure 7 Scanning electron micrographs of fracture surfaces of fatigue threshold.

(a) Mc: 520g/mol

(b) Mc: 1440g/mol

(c) Mc: 1960g/mol

(d) Mc: 3060g/mol

Figure 8 Transmission electron micrographs of side surfaces of the crack tip of fatigue threshold.